

CATION EXCHANGE BETWEEN COLLOIDAL CLAYS AND RESINS IN WATER AND AQUEOUS ALCOHOL AS A FUNCTION OF THE CONCENTRATION OF THE DISPERSED PHASE

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Exchange studies have been made between varying amounts of H-resins and varying concentrations of clays saturated with NH_4 , Mg and Ba ions. The amounts of hydrogen ions from the resin exchanged for the cations of the clays have been determined by titrating with an alkali. Experiments with the varying amounts of H-resin yield isotherms which are more or less similar in shape to ordinary adsorption isotherms in the case of Mg- and Ba- clays, but the slope is somewhat linear in the case of ammonium clay. The exchange of ions usually decreases with the concentration of the clay suspension.

Experiments have been carried out in aqueous as well as in aqueous-alcohol media, and the results interpreted in terms of the hydration of cations and on the basis of the concept that exchange takes place by an overlapping of the double layers of the two solid phases.

The immediate object of the work presented here is to evaluate the behaviour of exchangeable cations present in soil or clay towards a solid exchanging material. The ultimate aim is to use it as a basis for interpreting soil-plant root relationships. It is assumed that plant roots can adsorb ions from the surrounding soil by a process of ion exchange. But the procedure by which the exchange property of clays is generally studied is, more or less, arbitrary and little simulates the conditions obtaining in the plant-root zone. For instance, the exchange of ions is usually studied in dilute systems, and that too in presence of, perhaps, foreign electrolytes at a concentration quite inconceivable in the root zone. The usual practice is to extrapolate or apply, as it is, the information gained under the artificial conditions to the natural soil-root system. Brown and Albrecht (Res. Bull. No. 477, College of Agric., Univ. of Mo., 1950) recognised this artificiality and studied the exchange property of soils under conditions which simulated, more or less, those obtaining in the soil-root system. Their technique consisted in having a hydrogen system (clay or the plant root) separated by a suitable semipermeable membrane (collodion or cellophane) from the soil colloid, saturated with one or more kinds of ions. The membrane did not seem to prevent exchange and, what was more important, the soil-root conditions were simulated. Chatterjee (*J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2) also carried out experiments with H-resin, simulating plant roots, which were kept in cellophane bags, and thus separated from the soil colloid which was saturated with sodium, potassium and calcium ions, separately. The present work is an extension of this work (*loc. cit.*) with clays having exchangeable ammonium, magnesium and barium ions.

The ease of replacement of cations is known to depend on their size and degree of hydration. It is also known that in ethanol, in which the ions would be hydrated much less, if at all, the usual lyotropic series is reversed, so that ions are held in the order of their true ionic size and not in the order of their hydrated size. In order therefore to ascertain the role of ionic hydration in the exchange of the cations, experiments have also been carried out in aqueous ethanolic media.

EXPERIMENTAL

Known amounts of the H-resin were taken inside a small cellophane bag, fastened at the end of a pyrex tube, and moistened with water. It was then immersed into suspensions of base-saturated clays or clay salts of varying concentration, contained in a beaker. The contents were covered by paraffin sealing in order to prevent evaporation of water from the beaker. The system was allowed to remain in this condition with occasional cautious shaking, and the pH of the clay suspension in the beaker was measured from time to time with a glass electrode till it became constant. The equilibrium was usually attained within 5 days, but the arrangement was not dislodged before 7 to 10 days. The amount of exchangeable hydrogen in the clay suspension was then determined by titration with KOH in presence of KCl (Ganguly, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1417). This is equivalent to the amount of cation of the base-saturated clay which has been exchanged for the H-ions of the resin.

The amount of H-resin was varied in such a manner that the total amounts of hydrogen ion associated with it corresponded to 0.5 S, 1.0 S, 1.5 S and 2.0 S respectively where, S is the symmetry concentration. Results shown graphically in Figs. 1-3 record the variation of amounts of cation exchanged for the hydrogen of the H-resin with the concentration of the base-saturated clay suspension, and with the symmetry concentration of the hydrogen ions.

Three series of experiments were performed with ammonium, magnesium and barium clays in aqueous medium, in 30% and 50% ethanol. The base-saturated clays were prepared from Padegaon B type clay, which is a montmorillonite.

DISCUSSION

Sections (a) of the figures represent the amount of cation exchanged as a function of the symmetry concentration of the hydrogen ions in the H-resin, and sections (b) represent the amount of cation exchanged as a function of the concentration of the clay salt which is set against a definite amount of the H-resin.

The influence of the concentration of the clay on the ease of replacement of the cation saturating it for the hydrogen ion of the H-resin is clearly noticeable from the graphs in figures (b). Each cation appears to have its characteristic ease of exchange. In the case of the three cations studied here, the replacement is greatly hindered at high concentrations. This is much more prominent in the case of systems in which larger amounts of resin were used.

Figures (a) are similar to the usual exchange isotherms. The graphs for magnesium and barium clays have more or less the same form. The same for ammonium clay are somewhat more linear.

The decrease in the ease of replacement with the increasing concentration of the clay, as is particularly evident in case of the divalent clays, is most probably caused by the overlapping of the electrical double layers of the clay particles, thereby causing an "immobilisation" of the ions (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*).

In the case of the ammonium clay, the effect of concentration of the clays or of hydration on the exchange of ammonium ion is limited to the low concentration region (near about 2.5%), above which the exchangeability changes very little. The double layers associated with the clay particles appear to have come closest at a concentration of about 2.5%.

FIG. 1

Exchange characteristics of cations in aqueous medium.

FIG. 2
Exchange characteristics of cations in 30% ethanolic medium.

FIG. 3
Exchange characteristics of cations in 50% ethanolic medium.

Figures 2 and 3 show the exchange characteristics of the ions in aqueous ethanol media having 30% and 50% ethanol. It will be observed from Figs. 2 and 3 that the variation in the % exchange with the concentration of either clay or the amount of H-resin follows a more or less similar trend, viz., the % exchange decreases very sharply for the base-saturated clays as the concentration of clay increases; it increases in some cases nearly linearly, and in others according to the usual exchange isotherms, as the amount of the exchanging H-resin is increased. Apart from this trend, there is a distinct difference from a similar exchange study carried out in purely aqueous media. The decrease in the exchange of cations as the clay concentration increases, is much greater in water-ethanol medium than in water alone. Similarly, the release of the cations from the clays against hydrogen ions of the resins is considerably reduced in presence of ethanol, *i.e.*, the exchange isotherms of the clay-resin system have a flatter run.

Two factors which are likely to influence exchange in presence of ethanol may be considered. As a result of dehydration caused by ethanol, the double layers of contiguous particles overlap and the exchangeable cations are "immobilised"; so to say, this tends to lower the exchangeability as the graphs show. A similar feature is observed in the case of clay salts in purely aqueous medium when the concentration is high. The other factor, besides dehydration, which is likely to influence exchange in presence of ethanol may be the decrease in the dielectric constant and a consequent lowering of activity and a decreased exchangeability.

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